

THE EFFECT OF YOUTUBE VIDEOS ON LISTENING SKILLS OF ESL LEARNERS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This study investigates the effect of YouTube videos on the listening skills of ESL learners in Uzbekistan. Quantitative survey method was used and 40 students from various age groups and proficiency levels from beginner to advanced were selected. Data analysis indicates that most of the respondents frequently watch YouTube English content among which are movies, songs, vlogs, and educational videos. The learners expressed their views that they gained better listening comprehension (mean score 3.5/5) and vocabulary development (mean score 3.3/5). Besides that, YouTube was also highly valued for its accessibility, wide variety of content, and its usefulness in improving pronunciation and grammar. Although the findings are mainly based on learners' opinions rather than actual listening performance data, they still suggest that YouTube can serve as a useful supplement to traditional classroom learning in Uzbekistan.

Key words: YouTube, ESL learners, listening skills, vocabulary acquisition, Uzbekistan, digital language learning, learner perceptions.

Аннотация. В данной статье изучается влияние видеороликов YouTube на навыки аудирования у изучающих английский язык как второй язык в Узбекистане. Использовался количественный метод опроса, в исследовании приняли участие 40 студентов разных возрастных групп и уровней владения языком, от начинающего до продвинутого. Анализ данных показал, что большинство респондентов часто смотрят англоязычный контент на YouTube, включая фильмы, песни, видеоблоги и образовательные видео. Учащиеся отметили улучшение понимания на слух (средний балл 3,5/5) и расширение словарного запаса (средний балл 3,3/5). Кроме того, YouTube высоко ценится за доступность, широкий выбор контента и полезность для улучшения произношения и грамматики. Хотя результаты в основном основаны на мнениях учащихся, а не на фактических данных об уровне аудирования, они все же указывают на то, что YouTube может служить полезным дополнением к традиционному обучению в классе в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: YouTube, изучающие английский язык как второй язык, навыки аудирования, усвоение словарного запаса, Узбекистан, цифровое изучение языка, восприятие учащихся.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistondagi ESL o'rganuvchilarining tinglash qobiliyatiga YouTube videolarining ta'siri o'rganiladi. Miqdoriy so'rovnomasi usuli qo'llanildi va boshlang'ichdan yuqori darajagacha bo'lgan turli yosh guruhlari va malaka darajalaridan 40 nafar talaba tanlab olindi. Ma'lumotlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, respondentlarning aksariyati YouTube ingliz tili kontentini tez-tez tomosha qilishadi, ular orasida filmlar, qo'shiqlar, vloglar va ta'limiy videolar bor.

O'quvchilar tinglashni yaxshiroq tushunish (o'rtacha ball 3.5/5) va so'z boyligini rivojlantirish (o'rtacha ball 3.3/5)ga erishganliklari haqida fikr bildirishdi. Bundan tashqari, YouTube o'zining kirish imkoniyati, turli xil kontentlari va talaffuz va grammatikani yaxshilashdagi foydaliligi uchun ham yuqori baholandi. Tahlil asosan haqiqiy tinglash samaradorligi ma'lumotlariga emas, balki o'quvchilarning fikrlariga asoslangan bo'lsa-da, ular YouTube O'zbekistonda an'anaviy sinfda o'qishga foydali qo'shimcha bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkinligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: YouTube, ESL o'rganuvchilari, tinglash qobiliyatlari, so'z boyligini oshirish, O'zbekiston, raqamli til o'rganish, o'quvchilarning idroki.

Introduction. Nowadays, digital technologies play a significant role in helping ESL (English as a Second Language) learners improve their knowledge. Among these technologies, YouTube is considered one of the most important platforms for speeding up English acquisition, especially listening skills. By using this platform for educational purposes, learners can improve their listening because of the wide range of English content created by both native and non-native speakers.

Listening is often seen as one of the most difficult skills to develop. Improving this skill requires learners to be exposed to real English as much as possible. However, traditional classroom methods are not always enough. By using YouTube effectively, students can access authentic materials such as podcasts, movies, vlogs, and music, which help them improve their listening. Previous studies have shown that YouTube videos can positively influence learners' comprehension and engagement in language learning (Yaacob et al., 2021; Margawidjaya et al., 2024).

In Uzbekistan, access to YouTube was restricted for several years, and people often had to use VPNs. This has made it difficult to find research related to this context. After these restrictions were removed, learners gained easier access to YouTube, and many have started using it to improve their listening skills. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the effect of YouTube videos on the listening skills of ESL learners in Uzbekistan. It also explores learners' perceptions of YouTube as a learning tool and examines its impact on listening comprehension and vocabulary development.

Previous studies have shown that YouTube is a useful platform for language learning. For example, Yaacob et al. (2021) indicated that video content could help students enhance their listening skills by familiarizing them with real-life spoken language. Similarly, Margawidjaya et al. (2024) concluded that YouTube videos have a positive impact on student listening skills. In addition, Maphanga et al. (2025) showed that students find YouTube videos helpful for improving their speaking skills and boosting their confidence. However, the majority of these studies were conducted abroad, and there is still a research gap in Uzbekistan.

Results. This study employed a quantitative research design to investigate the effect of YouTube videos on ESL learners in Uzbekistan. A survey method was used to collect data from the participants. The study involved 40 ESL learners from Uzbekistan. They represented different age groups and various levels of English proficiency, including beginner, elementary, pre-intermediate, intermediate, upper-intermediate, and advanced. Most of the participants were female, with only a small number of male respondents. Data were gathered through an online survey made on Google Forms consisting of two types of items: multiple choice and Likert-scale responses. The first category focused on gathering demographic details about the students and their self-

reported preferences for using YouTube videos in their learning. The second category aimed to collect insights from students about the primary benefits and challenges of using YouTube videos from their perspective. In the second phase, participants completed an online questionnaire, which was available for a limited time before being closed. The responses to both categories were automatically collected and exported to an Excel sheet. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores for the Likert items, were calculated. The findings related to the benefits and challenges were analyzed and presented in various tables to highlight trends among learners.

Age:

35 responses

Gender:

40 responses

English level:

40 responses

Frequency of watching Youtube:

40 responses

Do you use YouTube to learn English?

38 responses

How often do you watch English videos on YouTube?

40 responses

What type of Youtube videos do you watch for learning English?

39 responses

Do you watch videos with subtitles in English?

40 responses

Watching YouTube videos helps me understand spoken English better.

39 responses

Youtube videos improve my vocabulary in English.

40 responses

I prefer learning listening skills through YouTube videos rather than textbooks.

40 responses

Discussion. The findings indicate that a large number of the participants make use of YouTube to help improve their English skills. A large number of the respondents

claimed to be regular English video viewers on the online media platform, with the majority stating that they watch English videos on a regular basis, whether this be every day or weekly. The selected videos for this study were either educational or entertainment such as movies, songs, vlogs and a mix of both. Majority of the participants always or sometimes watch videos with English subtitles. A surprisingly large number of our learners reported that watching YouTube helped improve their listening skills, with a mean score for the statement 'Watching YouTube videos helps me understand spoken English better' of 3.5 out of 5. This research also found that learners rated their vocabulary learning from YouTube at around 3.3 out of 5. This score reflects learners' perception of the opportunities provided by YouTube for vocabulary acquisition through the words and phrases found in video recordings. The results also indicate that YouTube is perceived as a useful tool for language learning due to its accessibility, variety of content, and interactive features. The participants highlighted the benefits of using YouTube for improving listening skills, vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar. The findings are based on learners' reported advantages of using YouTube to improve their listening skills rather than learners' actual listening ability. The study based on a sample of ESL learners in Uzbekistan reveals that YouTube is a viable teaching and learning tool that can be used in addition to a number of traditional resources to foster vocabulary acquisition and enhance listening skills. Exposing students to YouTube videos may inspire them to pursue additional English language learning opportunities.

Conclusion. The purpose of this research was to find out if using YouTube videos could help ESL learners in Uzbekistan improve their listening skills. Results from 40 individuals showed that the majority of learners habitually watch English YouTube videos, mostly with the aid of subtitles, and they acknowledge that the platform is quite beneficial to them in different ways such as enhancing their listening comprehension (average score 3.5/5) and vocabulary (average score 3.3/5). Besides that, learners still considered accessibility, multitude of authentic content, and the pronunciation and grammar help of YouTube as their main reasons for choosing this platform.

REFERENCES:

1. Margawidjaya, D., Herlina, R., & Irianti, L. (2024). *Fostering students' listening skills through YouTube videos integrated with Edpuzzle online platform*. Journal of English Education Program (JEEP), 11(2), 123-130. [https://doi.org/10.25157/\(jeep\).v11i2.15477](https://doi.org/10.25157/(jeep).v11i2.15477)
2. Maphanga, N., Maeko, M.S.A., Nkwanyane, T., Ramaboea, H., Nkosi, P., & Kola, M.I. (2025). Learners' perceptions of using YouTube videos in enhancing their communication skills. *International Journal of Educational Studies and Skills*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.33650/ijess.v5i1.11031>
3. Yaacob, A., Amir, A.S.A., Asraf, R.M., Yaakob, M.F.M., & Zain, F.M. (2021). Impact of YouTube and video podcast on listening comprehension among young learners. *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies (iJIM)*, 15(20). <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v15i20.23701>